

Figure S1. *Pal* biosynthetic gene cluster copies as a function of ASV occurrence across the 63-sample data set. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) was determined between the *pal* BGC copy number (3 gene targets for all 63 lobes) and ASV occurrence (n=461 ASVs across all 63 samples). The data is plotted according to the number of *Syngonium adareanum* lobes (samples) that the ASV was present in of 63 samples surveyed; only those present in 10 or more lobes (65 of 462 ASVs) are shown. ASVs were classified according to their persistence across samples (Core, Dynamic, and Variable are indicated³). If palmerolide A is produced by a microorganism, the microbe was hypothesized to be persistent, as the palmerolide A compound was ubiquitous across all 63 samples.